

Mapping Waldensian “Synagogues” at the Trial of Antonio Galosna, Piedmont 1388

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During the inquisitorial process against Antonio Galosna in 1387 and 1388, Galosna shared considerable information with inquisitor Antonio of Savigliano about the locations and membership of heretical congregations in Piedmont (routinely called “synagogues” in the primary material). In this brief analysis, we map these congregations and examine the numbers provided by Galosna. Our findings reveal disconnected dissident communities, with an equal number of male and female congregants across the entire area of interest. We further suggest that additional research into the discourse and interactions at the trial may reveal what factors informed the narrative from which such communities and networks are projected, hinting at the possibility that it may have been the result of the inquisitor’s interest in “mapping” heresy in space to better document it and develop more efficient strategies.

Reading the final entries in the record of inquisitor Anthony of Savigliano’s process from 1388, one cannot but picture the defendants tired and indifferent, slowly giving up on whatever little hope they still may have had as it gave way to horror. The inquisitor assembled a respectable party of legal experts, churchmen, and others of eminence in the cathedral church of St. John the Baptist in Turin, on Saturday, 5 September, and had the two men suspected of heresy brought there for all to witness the epilogue of their trial. One of this pair went by the name of Antonio (Anthony) Galosna who, after months of interrogation, incarceration, torture, threats, hope and despair, was at last about to hear that the inquisitor had little choice but to *release him to the secular arm* as a relapsed heretic. He was to die soon, for all he knew. Whatever else the inquisitor may have proclaimed regarding the confiscation of his worldly belongings must have been lost to Antonio in the echoes.

The testimonies that Galosna delivered before the inquisitor during the Autumn and Winter 1387 and Spring and Summer 1388 in Pinerolo and Turin before this sentence was proclaimed remain some of the best-known and most controversial pieces of evidence on mediaeval religious dissidence. First published at length by Girolamo Amati in 1865 and recently by Luca Patria and Piercarlo Pazé,¹ the record of Galosna’s interrogation digs into

¹ Girolamo Amati, “Processus contra Valdenses in Lombardia superiori, anno 1387”, *Archivio storico italiano* 37 (1865): pp. 3-52 & 39 (1865): pp. 3-61; Luca Patria, Piercarlo Pazé, “L’eresia diffusa: segmenti eterodossi nel Trecento alpino e subalpino (diocesi di Torino) secondo le rivelazioni all’inquisitore di Antonio Galosna e Giacomo Bech” in: *Valdo e Francesco. Inizi e sviluppi di due movimenti religiosi*, ed. Piercarlo Pazé (Perosa Argentina: LAReditore, 2016), pp. 131-251.

his dissident background, offers a few glimpses into the apparent syncretism of the sects of Piedmont, and quickly settles—as observed by Euan Cameron—on descriptions of congregations, their locations, and those present in what Cameron deemed the inquisitor’s “fishing for sexual scandals” and possibly for traces of magical practices among the dissidents.² But whereas much of what was written down at these interrogations regarding beliefs or particular practices leaves little room for outright compartmentalization, the record of Galosna “the wandering heretic”—an impressively detailed set of information on the many towns he visited, the local dissident leaders, and those present at (Waldensian) congregations – seems at first sight to offer insights that a quantitative approach may be able to uncover.³

Most of the record of Galosna’s interrogation, in fact, reads like a directory of heresy in Turin’s surroundings, covering considerable territory and some twenty years of Galosna’s wandering life, particularly the period from c. 1382 to 1387. He was usually able to provide considerable minutiae about the people he met—their professions, precise place of residence within each town, often even details about their relatives—but it seems he was rarely able to remember their names. Altogether, he mentioned some five hundred people as having taken part in a congregation at one time or another. This number, his ability to remember minute details (but not names), and the odd progression of his interrogation and trial—to say nothing of memory loss or confabulation—has cast doubt on the absolute veracity of everything he was reported to have said. He was famously threatened and tortured before none other than the Count of Savoy to retract his accusations against a pair of apparently well-connected men from Pinerolo, in addition to being tortured by the inquisitor. Needless to say, Galosna thrice testified about this particular case. After yielding to the requests of those he accused, he finally took his amended account back, claiming that all he had said earlier about these two was in fact true.

While one may be cautious of some details in his testimony, there is currently little reason to *outright* reject information on congregations. One must nevertheless beware of the context in which Galosna provided this information, which changed from one deposition to another. Records of Galosna’s (and not only Galosna’s) interrogation therefore require a mixed-method approach. But before research goes further beyond the text through a battery of methods borrowed from corpus and computational linguistics and discourse analysis— which may offer insight into mechanisms that governed his narrative in addition to (or beyond) memory—one must classify available information as a set compiled in an interactive and adaptive process playing out between the inquisitor and Galosna. In our current attempt to go beyond the text, we can perceive the data presented here as a series of snapshots of Galosna’s mind, frozen as it were in the moment(s) when the inquisitor inquired about whatever settlement he deemed important (following, no doubt, a mechanism of his own). Galosna, then, provided some information, which was probably far less than what he was capable of and yet conceivably more than he could have done in some other scenario. But it is a journey through his memory as it materialised at particular moments in the chambers of the inquisitor.

² Euan Cameron, *Waldenses. Rejections of Holy Church in Medieval Europe* (Oxford: Blackwell Publishers, 2000), p. 174.

³ Cf. Kathrin Utz Tremp, *Von der Häresie zur Hexerei: „Wirkliche“ und imaginäre Sekten im Spätmittelalter* (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2020), pp. 194–234.

Galosna mentioned nearly five hundred distinct persons as congregants at what the record identifies as (usually Waldensian) “synagogues”, *i.e.* dissident congregations in twenty-three settlements all over Piedmont. The picture that he paints is one of disconnected communities, each enclosed within its own settlement, rarely sharing any of its members. His narrative was one guided by spatial or even administrative considerations, enumerating his co-congregants as if they belonged to territorially defined groups. It was virtually only Galosna who, by his own account, ever visited more than one of these congregations.

Fig. 1. “The Star of Galosna”. A graph representation of the disconnected communities of Piedmontese congregations, with Galosna at the centre.

Of the twenty-three locations mentioned by Galosna, we have continued to map nineteen major settlements. This is either due to the scarcity of information on some of them (such as Cavour or Porte) or because some were at the time and still are only parts of larger towns (such as Borgo Paglierino, belonging to Avigliana). For the nineteen that were covered well, we have extracted information on the number of mentioned congregants and their gender, and we have mapped the spatial distribution of mid-to-late fourteenth-century Piedmontese dissidents as perceived and described by Galosna. And what he described in spatial terms is surprisingly prosaic: a set of towns with relatively normally distributed scores of total congregants ($W = 0.91$, $p = 0.1$) with a mean of $26.15 (\pm 5.77)$ and quite a lot of variation ($sd = 11.98$), with roughly equal proportions of male and female members with very few exceptions (overall $mean_{male} = 13.84 \pm 3.46$, $mean_{female} = 12.31 \pm 2.95$, Wilcoxon

rank-sum test $W = 203.5$, $p = 0.5$). The only notable exception is Andezeno, with nearly 78 % of dissidents being male.

Location	Total	Women (%)	Men (%)
Almese	20	10 (50)	10 (50)
Alpignano	10	4 (40)	6 (60)
Andezeno	40	9 (22.5)	31 (77.5)
Avigliana	23	10 (43.48)	13 (56.52)
Castagnole	19	9 (47.37)	10 (52.63)
Chieri	47	20 (42.55)	27 (57.45)
Coazze	44	23 (52.27)	21 (47.73)
Frossasco	18	10 (55.56)	8 (44.44)
Germagnano	12	5 (41.67)	7 (58.33)
Giaveno	29	15 (51.72)	14 (48.28)
Moncalieri	50	25 (50)	25 (50)
Pianezza	16	8 (50)	8 (50)
Pinerolo	20	7 (35)	13 (65)
Piovasco	36	21 (58.33)	15 (41.67)
Sangano	18	7 (38.89)	11 (61.11)
Scalenghe	15	9 (60)	6 (40)
Susa	26	13 (50)	13 (50)
Trana	29	15 (51.72)	14 (48.28)
Villar Focchiardo	25	14 (56)	11 (44)

Tab. 1. Locations and the reported number of congregants

Fig. 2. Deviations from the mean in the total number of congregants.

Research into each of the segments of Galosna’s network, or analysing it at lower scales, may offer some further insight into the mechanisms that may have shaped them from within in the first place. However, given that data at our disposal derive from a single set of (auto)biographical recollections, representing what we have characterised here as one of a number of possible “snapshots” produced at the intersection of the inquisitor’s interrogational tactics and Galosna’s reactions to them, it seems crucial to incorporate other factors that may have influenced a narrative that described such disconnected communities. In other words, analysing connections across the network (or rather lack thereof) ought best to go hand in hand with the analyses of the processes of interrogation and the narratives that shaped the data from which they are projected. This may offer answers to questions about what underlying dimensions led to such data: the deponent’s answers, the inquisitor’s curiosity, or the interaction between the two; the interest of the deponent, the inquisitor, or the notary in categorising things into spatial clusters, or indeed a spatially-minded approach to controlling dissidence—a disinterest in relationships between the various dissident centres (and the implied exchanges) and a profound concern about *where* to find heretics and strike at them?

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Locations of Waldensian congregations in Piedmont and their membership according to testimonies provided by Antonio Galosna in 1387 & 1388 in front of inquisitor Antonio di Settimo

- Locations mentioned by Galosna
- Proportion of male congregants
- Proportion of female congregants